

USING THE E-LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida elektron ta'lim muhitidan foydalanish haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raqamli iqtisodiyot, elektron ta'lim, raqamli ta'lim, raqamlashtirish, jarayon, kasbiy rivojlanish.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье представлена информация об использовании среды электронного обучения в цифровой экономике.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая экономика, электронное обучение, цифровое образование, оцифровка, процесс, профессиональное развитие.*

Annotation. *This article provides information on the use of the e-learning environment in the digital economy.*

Keywords: *digital economy, e-learning, digital education, digitization, process, professional development.*

In the conditions of the digital economy of educational institutions, the rapid systematic development of their electronic information and educational environment becomes a priority. In the short term, this is achieved by digitizing some of the traditional components of the educational process that have been developed at a high methodological level and tested for a long time. This includes the creation of video materials with lectures by leading teachers of fundamental and professional Sciences, the development of a test system, the creation of a fund of videos with technological processes necessary for the qualitative preparation of muiaxassis, etc. On the one hand, a significant part of these materials has already been prepared meaningfully and methodically and has been used in traditional educational technologies, so the digitization process can be carried out in a short time and with reasonable financial costs. On the other hand, they can be used in the implementation of various educational programs, while freeing the teacher's time to organize creative work with students in an individual mode. All this will be useful for professional educational institutions to create this block of digital content.

In the long term, in order to develop the digital educational environment of educational institutions, it is necessary to purposefully create a variety of online courses (both to include in the basic vocational education program and to contribute to the personal development of students), to introduce technologies and opportunities for communication in the digital environment, etc.

The difficulty of performing digitization tasks is due to the psychological inertia of some teachers and sometimes their active resistance to changes due to the expectation that their condition will worsen. It is also complicated by insufficient ability of scientific and pedagogical staff to develop e-courses, including poor knowledge of information and communication competencies.

The circumstances considered for the professional development system determine the strengthening of the share of training aimed at the development of psychological and pedagogical

competencies of teachers. Unfortunately, some teachers find it difficult to perceive pedagogical innovations, organizing their activities on the basis of outdated teaching technologies that they have learned. The problem of the transition to innovative educational technologies is exacerbated by the fact that most of the scientific and pedagogical personnel of educational institutions have only empirical pedagogical knowledge, which is not supported by a theoretical basis in the field of didactics of Higher Education.

It can be achieved by improving the pedagogical skills of teachers and forming their readiness to work in a digital information educational environment:

- to inform scientific and pedagogical personnel about the general trends in the development of professional education, structural and material changes taking place in it, the role of the teacher in the era of digital education. According to the results of this block, an understanding and internal acceptance of the wide introduction of digital education into the personnel training system should be formed;

- The formation of the readiness of teachers to develop the educational process on the basis of the use of the resources of the digital educational environment of the respuplika of Uzbekistan, first of all, mass online courses and moral qualities that allow students to significantly complement and deepen the study of educational content, develop their personal characteristics and spiritual qualities;

- the formation of its own e-learning resources, including the ability to create and use online courses.

This training includes two components – the acquisition of pedagogical and information and communication technologies (ICT). The pedagogical component is aimed at improving the level of knowledge in the field of didactics of the educational institution, the formation of a willingness to study the advanced technologies of professional education and the psychological and pedagogical features of their use in the implementation of specific educational programs, to support the individual personal development of students.

Today, knowledge of ICT allows the teacher to technically and technologically implement the teaching methodology at the digital level (by participating in the creation of teams of performers in the creation of mass online courses to develop e-learning resources on their own and place them in the national digital education environment);

- promotion of innovative activity of teachers through e-learning resource competitions, creative competitions on the use of the digital educational environment in the preparation of students; development of creative abilities of scientific and pedagogical personnel, promotion of pedagogical innovation are important.

The development of the digital educational environment of Professional education and the improvement of the skills of scientific and pedagogical personnel creates all the conditions for digitizing professional education, which involves the individualization of the educational process at the level of professional education and modernization, taking into account the expectations of each consumer group, and through ICT it is necessary to introduce

The task of modernizing education is being solved through a number of measures, including:

- Organization of professional development and training of personnel taking into account trends in economic development; this is facilitated by the design of an individual educational

trajectory for each student using professional educational resources from the digital educational environment of the Republic;

- the addition of traditional educational methods with different types of activities in the digital educational environment, which ensures participation in the development trends of the youth subculture and allows students to create a more flexible regime of mastering the professional sphere;

- strengthen the spiritual and moral development of students by expanding the courses of “digital” selection aimed at universal values; support for informal education in an electronic environment, including attracting the placement of their professional education in the minds of young people;

- ensuring the possibility of using professional education for people with disabilities in terms of mastering the skills and qualifications of professional activities using virtual laboratory workshops and simulators;

-support the creative development of talented students by accessing creative task databases and organizing interactive work of informal groups in a remote format;

-Organization of training groups of students of various forms and courses within the framework of interaction with industrial enterprises in the electronic information and educational environment of the University, Organization of project-based training based on the involvement of leading practitioners as specialists.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

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